

DFT Study of Magnetic Properties of Layered $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$

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Abstract—

TlGaS_2 is explored a promising layered compound for the development of 2D materials in spintronic devices and magnetic memory applications. The magnetic properties of the Fe-doped two-dimensional TlGaS_2 crystal were investigated using the DFT+U approach with parameter of $U=6\text{eV}$ within the spin generalized gradient approximation (SGGA). The pristine TlGaS_2 crystallizes in a monoclinic structure with space group $C2/c$ (No. 15). Our results demonstrate that magnetism can be induced in TlGaS_2 through substitutional Fe doping. The calculated total magnetic moment of the $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ system originates predominantly from the Fe 3d orbitals. This indicates that localized d-electron states of the dopant play an important role in generating the magnetic behavior.

The properties of monoclinic $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ are modeled by the ab initio method within the density functional theory magnetic properties of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ structure 32 atoms with Fe(Ga) substitution are calculated. The introduction of Fe(Ga) onto the TlGaS_2 induces the appearance of a local magnetic moment. The values of the magnetic moments are obtained, and the region of localization of spin density in the structure with 32 atoms which includes Fe doping is determined. The effect of the different atoms around of Fe substitution on the value of the magnetic moment in a $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ is studied. Modifications in the electronic structure strongly influence the properties of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$. The contribution of Ga and Tl atoms to magnetization is insignificant compared to that of sulfur atoms. The presence of sulfur atoms around impurity atoms in the structure significantly influences magnetization.

Keywords— TlGaS_2 , Fe, DFT+U, magnetic properties, 2D materials, spintronics

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INTRODUCTION

Two-dimensional (2D) materials have attracted considerable attention due to their outstanding electrical, optical, thermal, sensor, and magnetic properties, as well as their wide range of applications in spintronics. 2D materials have a wide range of properties, including metallic, insulating, semiconducting, semimetallic, ferromagnetic, and topological insulators. Atoms in

single-layer two-dimensional materials are linked by covalent bonds, while layered structures are bound by weak van der Waals interactions. Two-dimensional magnetic materials are important for the creation of new spintronic devices, such as those for applications in topological magnonics, spintronics, quantum computing, magneto-optics, and optical communications. New phenomena, such as the quantum anomalous Hall effect, magnetoelectric multiferroics, and magnonic

valleytronics, have been discovered using two-dimensional magnetic materials and their heterostructure configurations. The layered material exhibits intrinsic ferromagnetism, which is important for research into devices capable of localizing spin and two-dimensional magnetism. Magnetic materials also possess other properties, such as high charge carrier mobility, mechanical strength, and thermal conductivity [1-8].

The aim of this work is to study the electronic properties of doped two-dimensional photovoltaic structures TlGaS₂ using ab initio methods, for example, in the DFT+U model, to find compositions suitable for magnetic materials.

In particular, the 2D magnetic semiconductor TlGaS₂ [3] exhibits intriguing magnetic ordering, depending, for example, on the layer thickness and the nature of the dopant. However, the characteristics of bilayer TlGaS₂ [3] have been little studied theoretically. Due to the weak interlayer interaction, our recent studies have shown that bilayer TlGaS₂ can transition from an antiferromagnetic state to a ferromagnetic state under the influence of, for example, doping with d-elements.

Let's recall how the magnetic moment is formed in 2D compounds when doped with transition metals. The main source of magnetism is the unpaired electrons in the *d*-orbitals of the transition metal.

In 2D materials (e.g., graphene, MoS₂, h-BN, phosphorene, etc.), doping with transition metal atoms (Fe, Co, Ni, Cr, Mn, etc.) leads to the following: The inserted atom has unfilled *d*-orbitals (e.g., 3d⁵ in Mn, 3d⁶ in Fe, etc.). In a 2D environment, where there are fewer neighbors than in 3D, orbital overlap is reduced and electrons are less delocalized. Therefore, local magnetization increases. Such unpaired d-electrons can become localized because the 2D structure provides "gaps" (defective areas, vacancies, voids in neighboring regions) TlGaS₂-Cr [3].

Methodology

The equilibrium structure of TlGaS₂-Fe was obtained by relaxation using the generalized gradient approximation, the Perdew–Burk–Ernzerhof (PBE) model, and implemented in the ab initio simulation package ATK and Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package [1-3]. To account for weak van der Waals

interactions between layers, the DFT-D3 function was used. Interparticle interactions, including ion and valence electron orbitals of the components, were accounted for using projection augmented waves. The periodic functions of the supercells were expanded using a plane-wave basis set with a cutoff energy of 500 eV and a Gaussian spreading parameter of 0.05. The total energy difference was less than 1 meV, the force acting on the ions was less than 0.01 eV Å⁻¹, and the electron energy was less than 10⁻⁴ eV in self-consistent calculations. A 3 × 3 × 1 k-point grid was used for structural optimization and for calculating the system's characteristics. Spin-orbit interaction was taken into account using the PBE + SOC method. For improved band gap performance, the band gap was calculated using the HSE06 hybrid function [8].

Magnetic moment in 2D compounds. Let's recall how the magnetic moment is formed in two-dimensional compounds upon doping with transition metals. The main source of magnetism is unpaired electrons in the *d*-orbitals of the transition metal. In two-dimensional materials (e.g., graphene, MoS₂, h-BN, phosphorene, etc.), doping with transition metal atoms Fe leads to the following: The inserted atom acquires unfilled d-orbitals (e.g., 3d⁵ in Mn, 3d⁶ in Fe, etc.). In a two-dimensional medium, where there are fewer neighbors than in a three-dimensional medium, orbital overlap decreases, and electrons are less delocalized. Consequently, local magnetization increases. Such unpaired d-electrons can be localized because the two-dimensional structure provides "gaps" (defective regions, vacancies, voids in adjacent regions).

Mechanisms. There are three main mechanisms of magnetization in a doped crystal. Crystal field splitting. Depending on the symmetry (e.g., trigonal, tetrahedral, octahedral), the *d*-orbitals are energetically separated, and some remain unpaired. Exchange interaction. The conjugation of unpaired spins leads to the emergence of a magnetic state (FM or AFM) in the crystal.

Hybridization with the host state. In some cases, the d-orbital of the dopant metal can hybridize with the host p-orbital (e.g., C-*p* in graphene). However, with weak hybridization, the *d*-orbitals remain localized, and magnetism is retained.

The classical theory of magnetism in transition metals is known in combination with the DFT

description of localized orbitals. In general, magnetism is based on the following principles: Hund's rules + crystal field theory. They allow us to predict the distribution of spins and energy levels and why some metals have magnetic moments > 0 . Anderson model, Zener model, Stoner model. According to Stoner's criterion, magnetism is possible if:

$$I \cdot D(E_F) > 1$$

where I is the exchange interaction parameter $D(E_F)$ is the density of state at the Fermi level In 2D materials, if the doping increases $D(E_F)$ and there are highly localized states, then magnetism is possible.

DFT + Hubbard U (DFT+U) method allows for correct modeling of localized d -orbitals taking into account correlated electrons Fe. Numerical results for the properties of the doped TlGaS₂-Fe supercell show that the optimized bulk lattice parameters $a = 10.299 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 10.284 \text{ \AA}$ are in good agreement with experimental data. The calculated bond lengths and magnetic moments, as well as the TlGaS₂-Fe total energy of the doped system and the formation energy under various conditions, were calculated for the first time by us. It was found that Fe doped slightly changes the bond lengths in the structure. The covalent bond interaction between Fe and S atoms increases with increasing TM concentration. To study the stability of Fe doped TlGaS₂-Fe, the formation energy $E(\text{form})$ was calculated using the following formula:

$$E(\text{form}) = E(\text{doped}) - E(\text{pure}) + n(\mu_{\text{Ga}} - \mu_{\text{TM}}) \quad (1)$$

where $E(\text{doped})$ and $E(\text{pure})$ are the total energies of TlGaS₂ with and without Fe impurities. μ_{Ga} and μ_{TM} are the chemical potentials for the main Ga atoms and the Fe impurity, respectively; n is the number of Ga atoms substituted by Fe impurities.

Using data from known databases through the use of Machine Learning (ML), for example, in the DFT+U model, 45000 two-dimensional structures were studied to find compositions suitable for photovoltaics [9-15]

The observed [16] phenomenon has been discussed taking into account various interaction mechanisms between magnetic nanoparticles. External pressure

and defects may initiate the same type of electronic structure changes resulting in contradicting results in experiments[17].The theoretical background for triclinic and orthorhombic [18] spin Hamiltonian analysis is presented. The type of conductivity has been determined [19] from the temperature dependences of thermoelectric power of TlFe_{1-x}Ga_xS₂ solid solutions. This approach [20] of the Machine Learning U model is universally applicable, to significantly expand and solidify the use of the DFT + U method. Magnetic moments were investigated [21] in the DFT+U+V framework using first-principles self-consistent Hubbard parameters from DFPT and those predicted by the ML model. Have shown [22] that DFT+U+V, with onsite U and intersite V Hubbard parameters determined from first principles and self-consistently with respect to the structural parameters by means of density-functional perturbation theory, provides the most accurate description of the electronic structure of these challenging compounds. In [23] this work paves the way for reliable first-principles studies of other families of cathode materials without relying on empirical fitting or calibration procedures. Here [24] explained down-select the most desirable materials using band gaps and band edges obtained from Hubbard-corrected density functional theory. The current orbital solution scheme [25] aims to provide a more computationally accurate tool for electronic structure calculations of transition metal complexes and other compounds.

Results and discussion

3d-element-doped TlGaS₂ is a member of the ternary chalcogenide family, with a transition metal (Fe) and a layered structure. Below, we present the structures (Fig.1) and magnetic properties of TlGaS₂ doped with 3d transition Total magnetic moment is equal to 5.003 μB in TlGaS₂-Fe in case of Ga (Fe) substitution. The Mulliken population analysis determined that (Fig 1) the magnetic moment contributed by 8 Tl atoms were 0.102 μB , Fe-doped atom 3.764 μB , 7Ga atom 0.102 μB , and 1.032 μB by 16 S atoms. The magnetic moment enhancement due to the proximity of four sulfur atoms to the Fe doping was 0.696 μB . The contribution of Tl atoms to the magnetization remains weak than Ga atoms. The S atoms numbered, which exhibit the highest magnetization, are located in the immediate vicinity of the Fe atom.

The electronic structure [26-28] calculations demonstrates metallic behavior, with the density of states dominated by Mn (3d) and Fe (3d) contributions near the Fermi level. Calculations show that the parent TlGaS_2 is a semiconductor with a direct band gap of 2.62 eV (Fig. 2). Magnetism in $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ can be achieved by doping Fe with Cr, Mn, and Fe. The resulting total magnetic moment is primarily due to the 3d orbitals of Fe. Hybridization was detected between the 3d orbital of Fe and the 4p orbital of S in $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$. We also performed DFT + U calculations with $U = 6$ eV on Fe impurities to describe the strong electron-electron correlation. It was found that the magnetic moment of the dopants increased upon transition from the low-spin to the high-spin state. An analysis of the electronic structure of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ shows that systems with Fe doped transform into magnetic materials. These results can be used to develop the magnetic properties of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ in future experiments.

The effect of Fe impurity concentration on the dielectric properties of $\text{TlGa}(0.999)\text{Fe}(0.001)\text{S}_2$ thin films was studied in [29]. It was shown that the position and magnitude of the dipole polarization of charged particles are related to the Fe concentration. The density of states and defects affects the permittivity. The defect density decreases with increasing sample thickness, while the permittivity increases.

Using the DFT + U method, we found that polarized impurity states are primarily associated with the dx_y and dx^2y^2 orbitals of Cr [26] near the Fermi level in $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$. Polarized impurity states are shifted into the conduction band. In the case of a manganese-doped system, polarized impurity states are primarily associated with the dx_y , dx_z , and dz^2 orbitals of Mn near the Fermi level. And polarized impurity states are shifted into the valence band and cross the Fermi level. Polarized impurity states from the Fe- dx_y , dx^2y^2 , and dz^2 orbitals near the Fermi level are shifted deeper into the conduction band in the case of Fe doping. Therefore, the resulting magnetic moments increase to a high-spin configuration. From magnetization measurements it was found that the non-magnetic TlInTe_2 crystal exhibits ferromagnetic properties after doping with iron ions with a concentration of ~ 0.56 at.% [30].

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Atomic structure of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$: a) side view of the monoclinic unit cell of $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ and b) white arrows on the atoms in the figure indicate the magnetization of the atoms in the $\text{TlInS}_2\text{-Fe}$ structure

Practical significance. These findings can guide the experimental study of magnetic properties in TlGaS_2 . The results provide a basis for selecting the dopant concentration to design functional magnetic 2D materials, relevant for spintronic devices and magnetic memory applications.

diluted magnetic semiconductor for spin injection and spintronic applications.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. The first (a) electronic band structure of the $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ with the high-symmetry points $\Gamma\text{-Z}$ in the Brillouin zone. k_x, k_y is the momentum along the x and y directions and (b) density of electron states for d electrons Fe of the $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$.

Conclusion

Fe doping in TlGaS_2 is energetically favorable and induces magnetism. Fe atoms acquire a magnetic moment of $3.764 \mu\text{B}$, with charge polarization arising from localized Fe 3d electrons via p-d hybridization. DFT+U calculations demonstrate control over the magnetic moment and electronic structure. $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{-Fe}$ can transform into a magnetic half-metal and is a promising two-dimensional

References

1. Asadov M.M., Mustafaeva S.N., Guseinova S.S., Lukichev V.F. Ab Initio calculations of the electronic properties and the transport phenomena in graphene materials, *Physics of the Solid State*. 2020. Vol. 62. No 11. P. 2224-2231
<https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063783420110037>
2. Mustafaeva S.N., Asadov M.M., Guseinova S.S., Dzhabarov A.I., Lukichev V.F. Electronic, dielectric properties and charge transfer in a $\text{TlGaS}_2\text{:Nd}^{+3}$ single crystal at direct and alternating current, *Physics of the Solid State*. 2022. Vol. 64. No 4. P. 426–433.
<https://doi.org/10.21883/PSS.2022.04.53497.251>.
3. Asadov, S.M., Mustafaeva, S.N., Lukichev, V.F. Regularities of X-ray Transfer in Doped Multicomponent Semiconductors for Dosimetry. *Microelectronics*, 2025, Vol. 54. No. 2. P. 97–114.
<https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063739725600281>
4. Doping in 2D. *Nat Electron*. 2021. Vol. 4. P. 699.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-021-00668-9>
5. Zhao X., Xia C., Dai X., Wang T., Chen P., Tian L. Electronic and magnetic properties of X-doped (X = Ni, Pd, Pt) WS_2 monolayer. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 2020, Vol. 414. P.45-48,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2016.04.050>
6. Baithi M., Duong D.L. Doped, Two-Dimensional, Semiconducting Transition Metal Dichalcogenides in Low Concentration Regime. *Crystals*. 2024. Vol. 14. P. 832.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst14100832>
7. Dat V.D., Vu T.V. Layered post-transition-metal dichalcogenide SnGe_2N_4 as a promising photoelectric material: a DFT study, *RSC Advances*, 2022, Vol. 12. No 17. P. 10249-10257.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ra00935h>
8. Heyd J., Scuseria G.E., Ernzerhof M. Hybrid functionals based on a screened Coulomb potential, *J. Chem. Phys.* 2003, Vol. 118. P. 8207-8215.
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1564060>
9. Frey N.C., Akinwande D., Jariwala D., Shenoy V.B., Machine Learning-Enabled Design of Point Defects in 2D Materials for Quantum and Neuromorphic Information Processing. *ACS Nano* 2020. Vol. 14. P. 13406–13417. [PubMed: 32897682]
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.0c05267>
10. Yu M., Yang S., Wu C., Marom N. Machine Learning the Hubbard U Parameter in DFT+U Using Bayesian Optimization. *NPJ. Comput. Mater* 2020. Vol. 6. No 180. P. 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-020-00446-9>
11. Venturi V., Parks H.L., Ahmad Z., Viswanathan V. Machine Learning Enabled Discovery of Application Dependent Design Principles for Two-Dimensional Materials. *Mach Learn Sci. Technol.* 2020. Vol. 1. Article number 035015. P. 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/2632-2153/aba002>
12. Suzuki Y., Nagai R., Haruyama J. Machine Learning Exchange-Correlation Potential in Time Dependent Density-Functional Theory, *Phys. Rev. A* 2020. Vol. 101. Article number 050501.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.101.050501>
13. Tritsarlis G.A., Carr S., Schleder G.R. Computational Design of Moiré Assemblies Aided by Artificial Intelligence, *Appl. Phys. Rev.* 2021. Vol. 8. No. 3,
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0044511>
14. Masubuchi S., Watanabe E., Seo Y., Okazaki S., Sasagawa T., Watanabe K.,

- Taniguchi T., Machida T. Deep-Learning-Based Image Segmentation Integrated with Optical Microscopy for Automatically Searching for Two-Dimensional Materials, *NPJ. 2D Mater. Appl* 2020. Vol. 4. No 3. P. 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41699-020-0137-z>
15. Kirklin S., Saal J.E., Meredig B., Thompson A., Doak J.W., Aykol M., Ruhl S., Wolverton C. The Open Quantum Materials Database (OQMD): Assessing the Accuracy of DFT Formation Energies. *NPJ. Comput. Mater* 2015. Vol. 1. Article number 15010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npjcompumats.2015.10>
 16. M Maksutoglu, F A Mikailzade, MirHasan Yu Seyidov, T G Mammadov, A A Sukhanov, N M Lyadov, V F Valeev and R I Khaibullin, 2019, *Mater. Res. Express* **6** 076109
Doi:10.1088/2053-1591/ab1510
 17. Burak Gurkan and Savas Berber, Structural and electronic properties of layered semiconductor chalcogenide crystals: TlGaSe₂, TlGaS₂ and TlInS₂, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 96, September 2019, pp. 1123-1130
 18. Muhammed Açıkgoz, Paweł Gnutek, Czesław Rudowicz, Modeling local distortions around Fe³⁺ ions doped into TlGaS₂ crystal using superposition model analysis of the zero-field splitting parameters, *Solid State Communications* **150** (2010) 1077–1081, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssc.2010.03.008>
 19. S. Mustafaeva, S. Asadov, *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering, Charge Transport and Thermo-emf in TlFe_{1-x}Ga_xS₂ Solid Solutions*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/92853>
 20. G. Cai, Zh. Cao, F. Xie, H. Jia, Wei Liu, Y. Wang, F. Liu, X. Ren, Sh. Meng and M. Liu, Predicting structure-dependent Hubbard U parameters via machine learning, *Materials Futures* **3** (2024) 025601 (9pp), DOI 10.1088/2752-5724/ad19e2
 21. Martin Uhrin, Austin Zadoks, Luca Binci, Nicola Marzari, Iurii Timrov, Machine learning Hubbard parameters with equivariant neural networks, *npj Computational Materials* volume 11, Article number: 19 (2025)
 22. Timrov, I., Aquilante, F., Cococcioni, M., Marzari, N. Accurate Electronic Properties and Intercalation Voltages of Olivine-type Li-ion Cathode Materials from Extended Hubbard Functionals. *PRX Energy* **1**, 033003, DOI: 10.1103/PRXEnergy.1.033003 (2022)
 23. Timrov, I., Kotiuga, M. & Marzari, N. Unraveling the effects of inter-site Hubbard interactions in spinel Li-ion cathode materials. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **25**, 9061, DOI: 10.1039/d3cp00419h (2023)
 24. Gelin, S. et al. Ternary oxides of s- and p-block metals for photocatalytic solar-to-hydrogen conversion. *PRX Energy* **3**, 013007, DOI: 10.1103/PRXEnergy.3.013007 (2024)
 25. Macke, E., Timrov, I., Marzari, N., Ciacchi, L. C. Orbital-resolved DFT+U for molecules and solids. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **20**, 4824, DOI: 10.1021/acs.jctc.3c01403 (2024).
 26. Asadov, M.M., Mustafaeva, S.N., Huseynova, S.S. and Lukichev, V.F., Modeling of Structural, Electronic and Magnetic Properties of 2D TlGaS₂ Doped with a Magnetic Impurity, *Russian Microelectronics*, 2025, Vol. 54. No. 8. P. 1242–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063739725602206>
 27. Asadov, S.M., Mustafaeva, S.N., Mammadov, A.N., Lukichev, V.F. Modeling of Structural Properties and Transport Phenomena in Doped Multicomponent 2D Semiconductors. *Russ. Microelectron.* 2024. Vol. 53. P. 519–542. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S106373972460081X>
 28. Adhikary, T., Saraswar, A.K., Marupalli, B.C., Aich S., Oraon A., DFT studies of Mn-Al-Fe-C compositions to investigate electronic structure and magnetic properties. *Appl. Phys. A.* 2025. Vol. 131. No 8, 661, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-025-08777-4>
 29. Bakran H., Yakut S., Bozoglu D., Deger D., Mustafaeva S., Ulutas K. The effect of Fe content on the dielectric properties of

TlGa(0.999)Fe(0.001)S₂ thin films, Physica B: Condensed Matter. 2024. Vol. 685. Article number 416031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2024.416031>

30. Serdar G., Mammadov T.G., Najafov A.I., Berber S. Magnetic ordering in Fe-doped TlInTe₂ chain-like crystals, Physica B: Condensed Matter. 2026. Vol. 724. Article number 418142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2025.418142>